

From Directed Graphs to Deep Learning A Symmetry-First Conceptual Foundation

George Bird
Department of Computer Science
& Department of Physics and Astronomy
University of Manchester
george.bird@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

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Abstract

[Every section of this work remains incomplete]

The purpose of this work is to consider which symmetries are inherently preserved or broken by functional classes of general artificial neural networks predicated upon a particular, but arbitrary directed graph. Determining such considerations would make explicit which symmetries are preserved and broken when choosing a particular functional class primitive to use within a model. Hence, it provides a foundation for the taxonomic categorisation of deep learning primitives. This is intended as an effective theory for unifying symmetry within deep learning.

For mathematical readers: it is important to note that this is written to be straightforward as possible to understand the fundamental symmetries I wish to make clear, and therefore abuses of notation are repeated. These can be rigorously formalised if desirable, but my personal objective did not presently extend beyond making these fundamental symmetries emerging from directed graphs explicit. Hence, it remains a sketch, which I will likely gradually formalise with appendices, consider this so far a conceptual exploration, allowing notation, formalities to be loosely defined in the aim of making explorative progress which can be later followed with polish. My aim is making clear an effective theory, with the end goal is a unifying theoretical framework for symmetry in deep learning.

1 Introduction

The primitive-first approach has indicated that all the primitives of contemporary deep learning can be reformulated under various differing symmetries to reproduce alternative deep learning-like systems. From sets of such primitives, one can then choose from any particular maps to construct an artificial neural network computational model. The motivation of this approach is to identify the emergent foundational biases induced, and the compositional biases from their interactions — such as in the hybridised cases. Generally these choices exhibit particular symmetries, which are argued to be important for inducing similar biases into the network. The consequences of such symmetry choices is felt to be underexplored and the taxonomy is intended to systematically investigate the consequences each the chosen symmetry.

What this has made evident, is that the generalised class of artificial neural networks is not contingent on any particular map within its model. A specific artificial neural network is retrieved only when specific *choices* of maps are selected for computation. This has made clear that any particular primitive or map used in deep learning is not important for defining this general form of computational models. Therefore, to capture all generalised maps, the requirements for what is defined as an artificial neural network model is minimised such that it can encompass this broadest notion of what could fall under such a computational model. This generalised approach can be used to document all symmetries that are in principle enabled by this minimalistic model, before specific choices of maps are introduced which preserve only subsets of these symmetries.

Offering a rather high-level definition of what distinguishes an Artificial Neural Network (or Deep Learning) computation approach from others, one might qualitatively state “*Artificial Neural Networks are a Computation System Where Information Can Be Exchanged Between Neurons, and Both the Neurons and the Neuron-to-Neuron Connections Can Apply Any Map to the Information.*” This is so broad that it naturally encompasses all possible constructions of this manner, including those outside of the contemporary affine then non-linear sequences. It is from this foundation that the fundamental symmetries are assessed.

2 The Graph-Theoretic Emergence of Symmetry

In this section, the symmetries emerging from the architecture will be determined.

2.1 Defining Artificial Neural Networks Generally

From the prior qualitative statement “*Artificial Neural Networks are a Computation System Where Information Can Be Exchanged Between Neurons, and Both the Neurons and the Neuron-to-Neuron Connections Can Apply Any Map to the Information.*”, we can begin constructing functional classes of artificial neural networks in the most general manner, termed \mathcal{F}_{ANN} .

From this functional class, natural subclasses emerge given the particular neurons and their allowed connectivities being considered. One could consider each functional subclass defined by a ‘fundamental architecture’, which then includes all computations enabled upon such an architecture.

In such a definition, in lies a natural equivalence to directed graphs. Neurons can be represented as unordered nodes, V , whilst their interconnections can be indicated by a directed edges of the graph, $E \subset V \times V$. Together, $\Gamma = (V, E)$, these outline a basic connectivity, defining the architecture which all possible artificial neural networks models in that functional class are contingent upon.

Structure can now be continuously added to this underlying directed graph, producing a direct and lineage of objects until it recovers all possible artificial neural networks which could exist of this computational model predicated on it. Furthermore, it will then make explicit all choices and assumptions made which further restrict the functional class to the primitive defining maps chosen for a particular model — particularly, which symmetries that are inherent to the architecture are preserved or broken.

The first step in appending the directed graph with additional structure is determining the field, \mathbb{F} , used in computation. In what follows, this is assumed to be the real numbers, \mathbb{R} , or the complex numbers \mathbb{C} ; however others may be chosen such as quaternions etcetera with some generalisation. The directed graph becomes $\Gamma = (V, E, \mathbb{F})$, and the functional class defined by it is termed $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma} \subset \mathcal{F}_{\text{ANN}}$.

It is important to now determine what elements are present in the functional class \mathcal{F}_{Γ} , and give an intuition for how these relate to artificial neural networks. Particularly, this will require a consideration of matrix representations of the directed graph, which can be chosen in multiple ways but can be made equal with similarity relations for the same directed graph.

One common approach to representing a directed graph is an adjacency matrix. This indicates which nodes are connected by a directed edge and which are not. However, the vertices V are notably unordered¹. However, since this is a structured matrix, this imposes a particular ordering on those nodes for the purpose of representation. Therefore, we can consider one such representation, $\rho_E : E \rightarrow \mathbf{A} \in \{0_{\mathbb{F}}, 1_{\mathbb{F}}\}^{n \times n}$, where $0_{\mathbb{F}}$ and $1_{\mathbb{F}}$ are the additive and multiplicative identities for the chosen field and $n = |V|$. These will be expressed as $0 \equiv 0_{\mathbb{F}}$ and $1 \equiv 1_{\mathbb{F}}$ for simplicity².

Then we can imagine a map, which given the a specific adjacency representation of connectivity will express the functional class of all artificial neural networks contingent upon that adjacency. This is shown in *Eqn. 1*. An intuition for this functional class, is that every directed edge of the graph can be assigned *any* map of our field, $f_{ij} : \mathbb{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$ if in the representation $\mathbf{A}_{ij} = 1$. Then, when edges converge on the same node, the various values provided by such a computation must be aggregated as some other function, $f_i : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$, which can also be *any* map³. Hence, given this definition of artificial neural networks as edgewise and nodewise computation, this class naturally encompasses all possible models which could exist contingent upon the specific graph choice, which could be considered their fundamental architecture for connectivity. Here, \odot masks out those particular entries, since $\mathbf{A} \in 0, 1^{n \times n}$. Therefore, it acts somewhat like a hadamard product as will be detailed in *Eqn. 2*.

$$\text{ANN}(\mathbf{A}) = \left\{ (f_1 \ f_2 \ \cdots \ f_n) \left(\left(\begin{pmatrix} f_{11} & f_{12} & \cdots & f_{1n} \\ f_{21} & f_{22} & \cdots & f_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_{n1} & f_{n2} & \cdots & f_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \odot \mathbf{A} \right) \right) \left| \begin{array}{l} f_i : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F} \\ f_{ij} : \mathbb{F} \rightarrow \mathbb{F} \end{array} \right. \right\} \quad (1)$$

The action of a model within this functional class, $f_{\text{model}} \in \text{ANN}(\mathbf{A})$, on an input x can be considered for this given representation. If this model acts on n nodes, each with a value \mathbb{F} , then a representation can be chosen for the same ordering as ρ_E . This will be denoted ρ_V , resulting in $\mathbb{F}^n \ni \vec{x} = \rho_V(x)$. The model in this representation can be considered as the map $\mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^n$ as shown in *Eqn. 2*⁴.

¹Since we are not further restricting by assuming data structure, though one can trivially include this.

²Overall, I do accept that this section repeatedly employs mild abuse of notation, with the lack of dependence on V and ordering in the ρ_E definition, the later matrices of functions and how they act, their hadamard products etcetera. One can trivially (but lengthily) formalise this if desirable in a notationally correct way, but since it would obscure the main point it is left out for easier interpretability. My objective is to make clear graph based symmetries rigorously and not detracting from this with excessive notational formalisms.

³What will be termed ‘primitives’ are actually these particular choices of maps for f_{ij} and f_i , these can always be constructed as a functional class for the chosen primitive which actually specifies the subset of model being considered.

⁴Notably, this should be composed several times to propagate the node values through the overall network and contain identity maps to prevent mixing of differing timesteps of propagation. This will be later discussed.

$$\vec{x}_{t+1} = f_{\text{model}}(\vec{x}_t) = \begin{pmatrix} f_1(A_{11}f_{11}(x_1), A_{12}f_{12}(x_2), \dots, A_{1n}f_{1n}(x_n)) \\ f_2(A_{21}f_{21}(x_1), A_{22}f_{22}(x_2), \dots, A_{2n}f_{2n}(x_n)) \\ \vdots \\ f_n(A_{n1}f_{n1}(x_1), A_{n2}f_{n2}(x_2), \dots, A_{nn}f_{nn}(x_n)) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here, A_{ij} is the entry of matrix \mathbf{A} at the i^{th} and j^{th} index. Similarly for x_i as being the value at the i^{th} index of the vector \vec{x} in this ordered representation.

As stated, this is the functional class $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}}$ which is defined by the ordering of E used to produce *this* representation of the adjacency matrix. Differing adjacency representations of the same graph can be considered through differing node orderings.

For the same directed graph, consider two orderings of the nodes values into spaces \mathbb{F}^n , we can relate these by $\rho'_V = \pi \circ \rho_V$, as a result the adjacency matrix must transform as $\rho'_E = \pi^{-1} \circ \rho_E \circ \pi$, where π is an element of the permutation group, $\pi \in S_n$. Similarly, one can transform between functional classes using such permutations, for all $f_{\text{model}} \in \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}}$ then $\pi^{-1} \circ f_{\text{model}} \circ \pi \in \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}'}$. Considering the representations this can appear as $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}'} \ni f_{\text{model}'}(\vec{x}) = \mathbf{P}_{\pi^{-1}}(f_{\text{model}} \star (\mathbf{P}_{\pi} \vec{x}))$ for a matrix representation of the permutation, \mathbf{P}_{π} , in the same ordering. As a result, every element of functional class defined by one adjacency representation $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}}$ can be bijectively mapped to an element in a differing representation $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}'}$, since $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}'} = \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{P}_{\pi}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{P}_{\pi}}$.

Overall, the consequence is that $\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}} \cong \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{A}'}$, for all representations of the same directed graph. These effectively just result in notational differences due to the arbitrary ordering used in the representation, the end result of computations is the same as they are considered unordered. Hence, one can denote a particular representation as a sort of ‘special’ class to work with, \mathcal{F}_{Γ} — establishing the symmetries of this class can be mapped to all others using the above transforms. This chosen class, \mathcal{F}_{Γ} , will be used moving forwards. Overall, this can be interpreted as all artificial neural networks which are predicated on the particular underlying directed graph specifying the chosen architecture of study, and notated in one representation.

One may consider how this construction reconciles with the ‘computation by nodes’ statement, beyond the aggregator. There now exists several multivariate maps for sets of nodes which must be accounted for in such a construction $f: \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^n$, these may include softmax, layernorm or more recent isotropic functions.

There are in principle several ways to achieve this. One can just wrap each forward pass of the model in another function σ , which is defined not to break the existing graph structure of the model. Alternatively, one can move the computation off the nodes and into more edges, by just adding more nodes and fully connect them in sets to make these edges express the multivariate maps which were meant to be computed over nodes. It is believed this notational choice makes practically no difference in the resultant fundamental symmetries, beyond reinterpreting the consequences of the particular formulae. The latter notation will be assumed, computation over sets of nodes reexpressed as the addition of more nodes to which are fully-connected by edges to the set under consideration. Hence, one can continue working with the above functional classes without redefinition.

Similarly, batch-norm operates over the batch and probabilistic symmetries can expressed over time. The directed graph must just be appropriately stacked with the desired interconnections, or often termed ‘unrolled’, and this will recover such functions.

In the following sections, the primary objective of the paper will be moved towards: given a directed graph, what are *all* the possible symmetries which could act on the models. In effect, what symmetries are inherently preserved or broken by the graph architecture itself. Any particular network contingent upon this architecture can therefore not exceed these symmetries, they are the fundamental set from which symmetries can be chosen. This makes explicit the symmetries preserved and broken by the narrower selected functional classes which are actually employed within a given model construction, from which foundational biases and taxonomic analysis can take place.

These are considered ‘fundamental (linear) symmetries’ of the graph, which sit below closure, probabilistic and algebraic classifications. Since they do not depend on the specifics of any function constructed upon this graph, then the fundamental symmetries are derivable from the directed graph itself. They are therefore, the symmetries of all possible artificial neural network computation models dependent on this graph, listing all prospective symmetries which the chosen computations may exhibit. As an intuition, when you choose to implement a particular map along such edges, say affine maps ($\mathbf{f}(\vec{x}) = \mathbf{W}\vec{x} + \vec{b}$) then these cannot exceed the fundamental symmetries set out, and may often break many of them in selecting this particular primitive class.

2.2 Fundamental Symmetries of A Functional Class Predicated on a Directed Graph

This section will outline the conditions which determine which linear symmetries can act on an artificial neural network functional class. It will be subdivided into several sections, namely:

One will work with the adjacency \mathbf{A} throughout these sections.

2.2.1 Fundamental Symmetries of The General Graph

In this section, four primary relations will be constructed which determine symmetries of interest for the functional class \mathcal{F}_{Γ} . This initial section does not indicate all symmetries which can act on the functional class \mathcal{F}_{Γ} , as the other two

following sections will outline subclasses which can determine further prospective symmetries. The reason for such a choice in separating them, is for a systematic tabulation.

As stated, the desire is to find all actions which may act on elements within \mathcal{F}_Γ and remain inside the class, for any $f \in \mathcal{F}_\Gamma$. These outline all *closures* which are enabled by acting on a chosen functional subclass $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}' \subseteq \mathcal{F}_\Gamma$, an affine transform of f which remains within \mathcal{F}_Γ . In intuitive terms, this demarcates all symmetries which are not inherently broken by the directed graph's structure. Since, the functional class being considered, is any map acting edgewise along the edges defined by Γ , then those symmetries not inherently broken by Γ cannot be predicated on any structure other than Γ itself. This motivates the consideration of Γ alone.

In this light, we can begin shifting from a classical view of graph as discrete objects towards a more generalised, continuous-like, object. This is further allowed through the representations of the graph adjacencies using field \mathbb{F} which can be acted on by continuous affine transforms of the same field. This particular generalisation is atypical in approach, yet is permissible because it is not the symmetries of the graph persay, it is the symmetries of the functional class contingent upon the graph and these can be continuous.

Particularly this enables one to explore not just explore reorderings of nodes through permutations, but we can now consider general linear combinations, and affine actions, through transforms to the representations of these nodes. In this sense, the nodes act more like a basis embedded within \mathbb{F}^n , rather than each node being assigned only a single field, \mathcal{F} . Intuitively, this allows the nodes to be linearly mixed, resulting in redefinitions of nodes as linear combinations — but crucially those actions which preserve the connectivity such that one remains within \mathcal{F}_Γ . Hence, the objective is to determine which of these actions can be applied to nodes whilst leaving the structure of the graph invariant; therefore, remaining within the current functional class defined upon this architecture. This utilises invariances of the adjacency matrix, \mathbf{A} .

These basis alterations do not need to be normalised, they must merely *preserve* the current representation of connectivity (the structure of the adjacency matrix as the functional class definition). The principle is finding which actions can act as a change of basis of the nodes, whilst leaving the connectivity of the graph unchanged.

As stated, these actions do not need to leave the transformed adjacency matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, binary like the untransformed adjacency: $\mathbf{A} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$. Instead this transformed adjacency can take on values within $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}$ since it is generalised over a field, \mathbb{F} .

Furthermore, we are determining the symmetries of the functional class which allow *any* map along edges or at nodes, but must be limited by the specified connectivity. Therefore, a non-constant map cannot exist between nodes which are not connected by an directed edge specified by the graphs edges, as this would create a dependency not specified by the graph.

Hence, we are considering those actions that do not create an outgoing adjacency from any node to another which was not already present as an edge. Similarly, it should not create an ingoing adjacency from one node to another which was not already present either. These would fundamentally alter the computation graph, changing the functional class of allowed computations. However, the action can delete a connection within its existing connectivity, as this would result in a subset of the current artificial neural network functional class, since the edge can take on *any* function, including functions which are constant with respect to a particular input.

One can prevent edge *creation* by neccitating the relation: $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0}$ alongside the invertibility of the action \mathbf{G} pre- or post-composed with the adjacency matrix. Notationally, \odot is the hadamard product, with a matrix of ones, $\mathbf{1}$, and one of zeros, $\mathbf{0}$.

Hence, considering an action g on the connectivity, by its matrix representation $\mathbf{G} = \rho(g)$, two immediate symmetries can be realised as shown in *Eqns. 3 and 4* when considering the adjacency acted on the left, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{A}$, and on the right, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}$, by the action g respectively. To make clear, the allowed actions emerge in the same representation chosen for \mathbf{A} , to relate to other representations, one must transform $\mathbf{G}' = \mathbf{P}_{\pi^{-1}}\mathbf{G}$ and $\mathbf{G}' = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{P}_\pi$ for $\mathbf{A}' = \mathbf{P}_{\pi^{-1}}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}_\pi$.

$$\forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} = \text{supp}(\mathbf{A}) : \quad \mathbf{G}\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} \quad (3)$$

$$\forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} = \text{supp}(\mathbf{A}) : \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{A} \quad (4)$$

An interpretation of these is changing the codomain or domain basis for the artificial neural network's maps, $f : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^n$. The right action would constitute a basis change for the domain, whilst the left action is a transform to the domain. This can be considered due to the pseudo-associativity $\mathbf{f}'(\vec{x}) = (\mathbf{f}\mathbf{G})(\vec{x}) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{G}\vec{x})$, since $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^n$, $\mathbf{G}(\vec{x}) = \mathbf{G}\vec{x} : \mathbb{F}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}^n$, since $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n}$ is a linear action. Similar can be considered for the codomain on left actions.

For *Eqns. 3 and 4*, one can permit any such linear action. However, it will become useful to assign these to various subclasses for a more systematic approach. Although the fundamental symmetries of \mathcal{F}_Γ by definition includes all fundamental symmetries of its subclasses, it will be beneficial to consider these separately. It can be noted that any non-invertible action satisfying *Eqns. 3 and 4* will have the effect of moving functional class elements of \mathcal{F}_Γ into one of these differing considered subsets, by either effectivly removing and edge or creating a computational dependency between edges.

Therefore, purely for classification purposes, one can consider at this stage, only those invertible actions which do not collapse into one of these special subsets, since these will be considered separately. Since these actions can now be inverted, we can consider their collective group, \mathcal{G} , since g, g^{-1} and the defined identity can form this group. These group actions

are valid only in a given representation $\mathbf{G} = \rho_{\mathcal{G}}(g)$. This will be assumed moving forward and just denoted $\mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}$ for simplicity.

Therefore, in this section, we consider all such groups that satisfy *Eqns. 5 and 6*.

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} = \text{supp}(A) : \quad \mathbf{G}\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} \quad (5)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathcal{A} = \text{supp}(A) : \quad \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{A} \quad (6)$$

Eqns. 5 and 6 can be reexpressed, using the complement of the adjacency as a mask as shown in *Eqns. 7 and 8*, which can be more directly considered from linear algebra alone.

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A) : \quad (\mathbf{G}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (7)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A) : \quad (\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (8)$$

Generally, we would choose to only denote the maximal supergroup allowed by these, so if $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathcal{G}$, where all elements of \mathcal{G} satisfy one relation, then only \mathcal{G} will be considered. There may be several maximal groups satisfying these relations, all of which should be considered fundamental symmetries. Each flavour, a term used to describe a left, right or other action symmetry, may have the same or differing maximal groups.

We may also be interested in the basis transforms which transform the domain and codomain in equal step. For vectors, $\vec{V}_{\text{in}}, \vec{V}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{F}^n$, these would transform as follows: $\vec{V}'_{\text{out}} = \mathbf{G}^{-1}\vec{V}_{\text{out}}$ and $\vec{V}'_{\text{in}} = \mathbf{G}^{-1}\vec{V}_{\text{in}}$, resulting in the following action on the generalised adjacency: $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{G}^{-1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}$. This acts like a linear combination fully respecifying nodes outgoing and ingoing edges. This conjugate symmetry on nodes is given by the group criterion displayed in *Eqn. 9*. These are enabled only when a symmetry can concurrently satisfy both left and right conditions at the same time. These indicate which symmetries are preserved by the graph's connectivity over nodes, the transform of these nodes simultaneously preserves edges ingoing and outgoing from these nodes.

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A) : \quad (\mathbf{G}^{-1}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

A further, and seemingly unusual, symmetry can be ascertained if we choose to consider a transform of nodes but by actions in differing representations. Particularly, considering a subset of nodes in the domain $\{a, b, c\}$ and their paired dependence to a subset of nodes in the codomain $\{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$. Considering the representations of node permutations, one can consider the permutation $\tau: (a \rightarrow \alpha), (b \rightarrow \beta), (c \rightarrow \gamma)$, as \mathbf{P}_{τ} . One can then recompute the conjugate group actions on this altered graph as shown in *Eqn. 10*. This indicates what symmetries can commute with the edgewise computations.

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A) : \quad (\mathbf{G}^{-1}\mathbf{P}_{\tau}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{P}_{\tau}\mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (10)$$

[Finish interpretation of these]

[Translations act trivially, since they don't change connectivity only nodes]

[How these can be computed simply, by looking at rows and columns which are equal, e.g. the intersection of orthogonal complements of the each rows/columns span, or the intersection of them both etc]

We must now proceed to considering the fundamental symmetries of subclasses, to determine all fundamental symmetries of the overarching class of interest \mathcal{F}_{Γ}

2.2.2 Functional Subclasses: Enclosed Architectures

Within a specified directed graph they're may include a simpler directed graph. For example, a directed graph $\Gamma' = (E', V')$ we could consider another graph $\Gamma = (E, V)$ such that for all $e \in E'$ and for all $v \in V'$, there exists also $e \in E$ and $v \in V$ where $E \neq E'$. Therefore, the resultant functional classes $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'} \subset \mathcal{F}_{\Gamma}$, since $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'}$ would be all those models where the edgewise computation on E is constant where there exists no edge in E' .

Similarly this can be shown with adjacency matrices in the same representation: $\mathbf{A}' \neq \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}' \odot \mathbf{A}$. Therefore, a nested structure is produced $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma''} \subset \mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'} \subset \mathcal{F}_{\Gamma}$, which eventually reduces to a disconnected graph. Hence, to determine all linear symmetries which may act on any element of \mathcal{F}_{Γ} , we must also consider these subsets $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'}$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma''}$.

Considering these separately has advantages, since a particular one may consider the same subgraph for two non-equivalent supergraphs; hence, for tabulating fundamental symmetries in a systematic way, these can be considered separate, and a supergraph then contains all fundamental symmetries of its subgraphs.

Overall, these relations are the same as before but for the functional class predicated upon this subgraph:

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A') : \quad (\mathbf{G}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A') : \quad (\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{G}) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (12)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A') : \left(\mathbf{G}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{G} \right) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (13)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{G} \in \mathcal{G}, \forall \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \text{supp}(A') : \left(\mathbf{G}^{-1} \mathbf{P}_\tau \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{G} \right) \odot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{P}_\tau \mathbf{A}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

Non-invertible symmetries of \mathcal{F}_Γ move you into a subclass \mathcal{F}_Γ

All supergraphs must also admit the symmetries of ANNs on subgraphs, so these can be appended as fundamental symmetries.

In other words, if you choose to use a fundamental symmetry which is specific *to this* subclass, it will force you into a functional form of this type. The result is trivial otherwise, one can reduce the graph to no connections and always commute etc.

2.2.3 Functional Subclasses: Edge Equivalences

One can now consider a subclass of the functional class \mathcal{F}_Γ which is not itself a subset of a functional class of any subgraphs, $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'}$. For example, for all $\Gamma' \subset \Gamma$, then consider \mathcal{L} 's such that $\mathcal{F}_{\Gamma'} \subset \mathcal{L} \subset \mathcal{F}_\Gamma$. These are peculiar and can increase upon the symmetries of the superclass \mathcal{F}_Γ .

These are equivalent to considering a modified graph $\Gamma = (V, E, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{E} indicates edge computational interdependencies. In effect, for $E_1, E_2 \in E$ and $(E_{21}, E_{20}) \in \mathcal{E}$, then the functional class defining computations from nodes indexed 1 to 2 and 0 to 2 are not independent.

One can consider a basis $\mathbf{T}_{\alpha i, j}$ for the support of $\mathbf{A} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$, where $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{F}^{n \times n \times n}$, with $\mathbf{T}_{\alpha i j} (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{A})_{ij} = \mathbf{0}_{\alpha i j}$. These edgewise computation interdependencies can then be considered for when there is a functional subclass defined by $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{F}^{m \times n \times n}$, for $m < n$. This requires a redefinition of ANN, but principally is that it relates the computations on — in other words a general computation symmetry which can result in parameter sharing phenomena with enriched symmetries.

These additional symmetries emerge as the orthogonal complement of spaces spanned by rows or columns defined by the span of \mathbf{T} , which can now be different since $m < n$.

In other words, if you choose to use a fundamental symmetry which is specific *to this* subclass, it will force you into a functional form of this type. The result is trivial otherwise, one can reduce the graph to no connections and always commute etc.

2.2.4 The Nature of Symmetries for General Non-Linear versus Affine Maps

One may note that, the symmetries derived are currently applicable to only affine transforms. The aim of this section is to first show that general first-differentiable maps cannot exceed the fundamental symmetries of affine transforms, then proceed to show this for general maps.

Then show that non-linear maps cannot exceed the maximal symmetries of affine maps of the same architecture

One can just do Taylor expansion of the non-linearity if it is first differentiable. This returns an affine map plus higher order (potentially non-linear) maps. So first differentiable maps, have maximal symmetries enveloped by affine symmetries.

Then show this for general functions, whilst considering incomputable/pathological functions carefully.

2.3 Overall Interpretation of The Meaning of These Symmetries

The result is trivial otherwise, one can reduce the graph to no connections and always commute etc. So you want to choose the minimal superclass which covers your functional class with the directed graph and computational interdependencies.

3 Examples

3.1 How to Find the Fundamental Symmetries of Your Artificial Neural Network

4 The Amended Taxonomy

5 Conclusion

References